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The Role of Nṛsimhapūrvottaratāpanīyopaniṣads in Human Life

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Abstract

The Atharva-Vedic minor and Vaiṣaṇava sect's Nṛsimhapūrvottaratāpanīyopaniṣads is an upaniṣads. This upaniṣads describe Nṛsimhadeva. Here, he is characterized as being half man and lion. He is the creator of justice and the destroyer of injustice. Nṛsimhadeva shields him from all threats, just as a mother shields her child, if anyone, from the highest to the lowest echelons of society, continuously meditate him. Regular chanting of the various tattva mentioned in this upaniṣads, including praṇava-tattva, ṣaṭcakra and mantrarāja-ānuṣṭubha, results in the blessings of Nṛsimhadeva. The extent of Nṛsimhadeva's influence in human life is recorded in this article by describing these theories.

Keywords

Neglect, Salvation, Worship, Violence, Sections, Injustice, Spirituality, Purity, Hatred.

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Introduction

The Atharva-Vedic minor upaniṣads of Vedic literature include the Nṛsimhapūrvottaratāpanīyopaniṣads. There are two sections to it- Nṛsimhapūrvatāpanīyopaniṣat and Nṛsimhottaratāpanīyopaniṣat. These two upaniṣads are referred to as secondary upaniṣads because Śaṅkarācārya did not write any commentaries on them. The fourth incarnation of Lord Viṣṇu, Nṛsimhadeva, is described in this upaniṣat. For this reason, this upaniṣat is associated with Vaiṣṇavism. In other words, this upaniṣat belongs to the minor Vaiṣṇava sect of Atharva-Vedic.

This upaniṣat described Nṛsimhadeva. He is half lion, half human. He is creator of justice and the destroyer of injustice. Fear, jealousy, hatred and neglect are all destroyed by Nṛsimhadeva. He demonstrates how to live a life free from injustice, hatred, fear and violence. He is a representation of courage and faith. He is reality's knowledge. He is the one who bestows salvation. Worshipping him fosters spiritual attitude, self-awareness and self-satisfaction. Worshipping him awakens spirituality and brings about mental purity. One can comprehend the unity of soul and Brahman by worshipping him. Ṣaṭcakra, Praṇava, Sāvitrī mantra, Yajurlakṣmī mantra, Sāmāṅga, Śaktivījasvarūpa svaras and other upaniṣads are significant to human existence. This Nṛsimhadeva's most significant mantra is- *ugraṁ vīraṁ mahāviṣṇuṁ/ jvalantaṁ sarvato mukhaṁ/ Nṛsimhaṁ bhīṣaṇāya bhadrāṁ/ mṛtyumṛtyuṁ namāmyahaṁ.*

Nature of the Study

This is a description of Nṛsimhadeva's glory. Brahman can't be attained without studying Nṛsimhadeva. Chanting Lord Nṛsimhadeva on a regular basis makes one omniscient. Nṛsimhadeva helps him grow mentally, socially and physically raises him to the top.

Background of the Study

The topic covered in this upaniṣads are found in other upaniṣads and books. For instance, the Māṇḍukyopaniṣat, Muṇḍukopaniṣat and Svetasvataropaniṣat-which are regarded as the background of this book are mentioned either directly or indirectly.

Scope of the Study

On this article, there are numerous excellent works. By this topic, the philosophical significance of this upaniṣads, its practically, the six cakras on

human life that are mentioned in both the Nṛsīṃhapūrvottaratāpanīyopaniṣads and the Viṣṇupurāṇa etc.

Major Research Gaps of the Study

There is a workaround in this article. Nṛsīṃhadeva, for instance, has the potential to use historical-comparative and analytical. The social implications of these upaniṣads can be discussed.

Methodology of the Study

This article is exploratory in nature. Both primary and secondary sources are used to discuss the article. Here, historical and analytical method are used as needed.

Questions

- How can one achieve amṛtattva?
- Who are not allowed to meditate sāvitrī?
- What is the Nṛsīṃha-gāyatrī?
- How many letters are there in Praṇava?

Nṛsīṃhapūrvottaratāpanīyopaniṣads

Outcome of Praṇava

The awoken stage (jāgarita-sthāna) is the first step (pāda) of praṇava, comprising these matters are like bahiḥprajña-saptāṅga-ekonaviṃśatimukhaḥ-sthūlabhuk and vaiśvānara.¹

The dream stage (Svapna-sthāna) indicates the second step (pāda) of praṇava, existing these matters are antaḥprajña-saptāṅga-ekonaviṃśatimukhaḥ-praviviktabhuk and tajasa.²

The dormancy stage (suṣupta-sthāna) is the third step (pāda) of praṇava. It's neither a dormant nor a dream stage. Suṣupta-sthāna is ānandabhuk, prājña and prajñānaghana.³

The fourth stage (turīyābasthā) is the fourth step of praṇava. This is neither antaḥprajña, nor bahihprajña, nor both prajña, nor prajña, nor aprajña, nor prajñānaghana-adṛśya-impractical-imperceptible-alakṣaṇa-acintya-abyapadeśa-ekatmā-pratayasāra-prapañcasāma-śanta-śivaṁ-advaita is considered the turīya and that ātmā.⁴ Tūryatūrya is the witness of everything, these are-cakṣu-karṇa-prāṇa-vāka-mana-tama e.i. the witness of everything.⁵ Those vīra (heroes) are able to destroy everything by knowing tūryavidyā through mantrarāja-nārasimha-ānuṣṭubha. However, if it consistently appears and becomes ineffective due to ignorance.⁶

If one who worships omkāra gets the blessings of Nṛsimhadeva and he can conquer the death. Nṛsimhadeva roots out all ignorance of a person by meditating on omkāra. Even if meditator can feel no distance between him and brahma and they become one and the same. Get rid of from all the sins and sorrows of the meditator's mind becomes free and not to be obligated by reincarnation and he proceeds on the path of salvation.

Outcome of Ṣaṭcakra

1. Ṣaḍaracakradarśana: - Six folds (aura) are classified here. Six leaves and six seasons are denoted by the six words. Amidst the six leaves the navel and the auras also exist in them. The whole cakra is implemented by māyā doesn't keep in touch to the soul and the six cycle (cakra) from the outside is enclosed by māyā.⁷
2. Aṣṭāracakradarśana: - Eight aura cakra are coined with eight letters having in each line of the prosody and including eight auras in it. The aura of this cakra is equal to eight letters of the Gāyatrī prosody (canda) and outside is covered by māyā extended in every matter.⁸
3. Dvādaśāracakradarśana: - This cakra belongs to twelve characters. Compared this twelve letter cakra with the Jagatī prosody, containing twelve letters each enclosed by māyā.⁹
4. Ṣoḍaśāracakradarśana: - Comprising sixteen auras in it and sixteen auras of Nṛsimha are included in dala. Nṛsimha is known by God by the sixteen cakra veiled by māyā because of spirit (māyā) doesn't make touch the soul.¹⁰
5. Dvātriṅṣaṭauracakradarśana: - Thirty-two folds are classified into thirty-two auras, various similarities also found in the Anuṣṭubha prosody which is the thirty-two akṣarā. Each letter has each aura veiled by māyā on the outside.¹¹

6. Avayavadarśana: - Previous auras, pañcāvayavarās are attired in the cakra like prosody and having individual forms.¹²

Who doesn't know about the ṣaṭcakra of Nṛsimhadeva, aftermath, supposed, he knows nothing and his ineffectiveness of vedādhyāyana. Who knows the mahācakra properly achieves the prominent position. If anyone suppressed the ṣaṭcakra might be teacher (Guru) and omniscient (sarvomantrapadestā). Worshipper of the Nṛsimhānuṣṭubha receives the grace of ṣaṭcakra who makes assist to relief from demise and demon. Therefore, the person should be aware the importance of the ṣaṭcakra from the master (Guru). To achieve bhū-bhuvah-svah need chanting the Nṛsimhadeva. Even if, he wins Mahācakra, tapoloka and satyaloka.

He himself fascinates to God, demon and man by praying day-to-day the Nṛsimhadeva.¹³

By worshipping daily of Nṛsimhānuṣṭubha obtain blessings and prosperity of Agniṣtomayoga, Āptoryāma, Vājapeyayāga and Aṣmedhayāga. Moreover, who chants regularly Nṛsimhadeva receive auspicious impact from caturveda and purāṇa and be aware of the praṇava doctrine. The Nṛsimha's mantra is worshipped become sacred like the fire and the air, except that to be sinless like Brahma-Viṣṇu-Rudra etc.

This cakra establishes fulfilment the expectant of the followers. Nṛsimha's ṣaṭcakra is the liberator of path and emblem of Parabrahma in Ṛg-yaju-sāmaveda. The followers are free from all sorrows and all sins while chanting the Nṛsimha's ṣaṭcakra. Those who compose ṣaṭcakra, the saviour for all devotees like parents, flourish their mental peace and leave out mental barriers. If we abstain from the Nṛsimha's ṣaṭcakra faded away all happiness from our life. Cakras are easy to perceive but difficult to make out as graph of the insight world, consisting joy, energy, love, creativity, intuition and spirituality. A disease-free life is possible through proper practicing of cakras. To stay healthy is needed deeply meditation of cakra and yoga. Energy imbalance of a person cakra is related to specific emotions consequently needed daily meditation of cakra and yoga, by which our physique solves various problems, maintains physical balance and provides mental peace.

Outcome of Mantrarāja-ānuṣṭubha

The highest position will be attained by someone who consistently studies the mantrarāja-ānuṣṭubha. This individual becomes the agnipūto, vāyupūto, ādityapūto, somapūto, satyapūto, Brahmapūto and sarvapūto.

Daily recitation of the mantrarāja-ānuṣṭubha he achieves death and sin. In other words, he puts an end to everything. Anī-vāyu-āditya-soma and udaka can all be stunned by that individual and is capable of stunning all Gods, planets and poisons. If anyone everyday studying the six cakras he attracts Gods, yakṣas, snakes to oneself. In other words, he attracts everything to himself. He subdues the three lokas that chanting Nṛsiṃhadeva. Bhūr-bhūva-svaḥ and mahāḥloka, satyaloka and sarvaloka.

Findings

Nṛsiṃhadeva protects anyone who practices praṇava irrespective of class creed and gender, even benevolent-ship showers upon a śūdra-women, a prostitute etc also. Praṇava impart in harmony, truth and balance. These values influence social behaviour such as respect, non-violence, self-control and peaceful coexistence. Collective chanting of praṇava is believed to promote calmness and reduce stress contributes to peaceful social interactions and emotional well-being in communities. The ṣaṭcakra is the crown jewel of Nṛsiṃhadeva. By meditating this cakra one gets the blessings of Nṛsiṃhadeva. Due to awakening and practicing of these six cakras the terrible diseases of the body are also cured. The ṣaṭcakra helps to get rid of both mental, spiritual and psycho-physical ailments. The ṣaṭcakras are the gateway of salvation.

Limitation

The results of this study are different according to the information, time, researcher and according to the method. These matters are considered to be the limitation of this study.

Endnotes

1. ...jāgaritasthāno bahihprajñāḥ saptāṅga ekonaviṣatimukhaḥ sthūlabhugvaiśvānaraḥ prathamāḥ pādah
Nṛsiṃhatāpanīyopaniṣat-pūrvatāpani-caturthopaniṣat-mantra number-4. p 206.
2. ...svapnasthāno 'ntahprajñāḥ saptāṅga ekonaviṣatimukhaḥ praviviktabhuk taijaso dviṭīyah pādah
ibid. Mantra number-5. p 207.

3. ...*yatra supta na kañcana kāmam kāmāyate na kañcana svapnam paśyati tat susuptam/ susuptasthāna ekibhūta prajñanaghana evānandamayo hyanandabhuk cetomukhaḥ prājñastṛīyaḥ pādaḥ*
ibid. Mantra number-6. p 207.
4. ...*nāntaḥprajñam na bahiḥprajñam nobhayataḥprajñam na prajñam nāprajñam na prajñanaghanamadṛṣtamavyavahāryamagrāhyamalakṣaṇamacintyamavyapadeśyama ikātma pratayasāram prapañcōpaśam śāntam śivamadvaitam caturtham manyate sa ātmā sa vijñeya.*
ibid. Mantra number-7. p 207.
5. ...*cakṣaḥ sāksī śrotasya sāksī vāca sāksī manasaḥ sāksī buddheḥ sāksī prāṇasya sāksī tamasaḥ sāksī sarvasya sāksī.*
ibid. Nṛsimhatāpanīyopaniṣat-uttaratāpani-2nd khanda- mantra number-3. p 227.
6. ...*eṣa vīro vīro nārasimhena vānuṣṭubhā mantrarājena turīyam vidyādeṣa hyātmānam prakāśayati sarvasamhārasamathaḥ paribhavāsahaḥ prabhurvyāptaḥ sadojjvali 'vidyātkāryahīnāḥ*
ibid. Mantra number-11. p 245.
7. ...*ṣaḍauram vā etat sudarśanam mahācakram tasmāt ṣaḍauram bhavati ṣaṭcakram cakram bhavati ṣaḍvā ṛtavaḥ ṛtubhiḥ sanmitam bhavati madhye nābhirbhavati.*
ibid. Mantra no-2. p 298
8. ...*Aśṭāramastapatram cakram bhavatyāṣṭākṣarā vai gayatri gāyatrī sanmitam bhavati vahirmāyayā veṣṭitam bhavati kṣetram kṣetram vai māyaisā sanpadyate.*
ibid. Mantra no-3. p 299
9. ...*dvādaśāram dvādaśapatram cakram bhavati dvādaśākṣarā vai Jagatī jagatyā sanmitam bhavati vahirmāyayā veṣṭitam bhavati.*
ibid. Mantra no-4. p 299
10. ...*Ṣoḍaśāram ṣoḍaśapatram cakram bhavati ṣoḍasakalo vai puruṣaḥ evedam sarvam puruṣeṇa sanmitam bhavati māyayā vahirbestitam bhavati.*
ibid. Mantra no-5. p 293
11. ...*Dvātrinsadauram dvātrinsatpatram cakram bhavati dvātrinsadakṣarā vā anuṣṭubhavatyānuṣṭubhā sarvamidam bhavati vahirmāyayā veṣṭitam bhavati.*
ibid. Mantra no-6. p 294
12. ...*Auravā etat suvaddham bhavati vedā vā ete atāḥ patairvā etat sarvataḥ parikrāmati candāmsi vai patrāṇi.*
ibid. Mantra no-7. p 295

13. ...*ya evataṁ mantrarājām Nārasimhānuṣṭubhaṁ nityamadhīte sa manuṣyānākarṣayati sa devānākarṣayati sa nagānākarṣayati sa yaṣānākarṣayati sa sarvānākarṣayati.*
ibid. Mantra no- 1. p 296

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